

Separation of Coumarins

R. S. Shah and S. L. Bafna

The separation of mixtures of some coumarins is described using a strongly basic anion exchange resin, Amberlite IRA-400, in the chloride form.

Earlier¹, a study of column sorption-desorption of coumarin and of relative column sorption of some methyl-, methoxy- and hydroxycoumarins was reported. In this study, the separation of mixtures of some coumarins² at room temperature ($\sim 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) is described.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin used was a strongly basic anion exchanger, Amberlite IRA-400 (Rohm and Haas); this and the chemicals used were from the samples used in the earlier work^{1,2}.

Procedure: A column of the resin Amberlite IRA-400 in the hydroxyl form was set up. The column data were: moisture content of the air-dry resin=21.15%; capacity of the air-dry resin per gm=2.036 meq.; capacity of the resin in the column=20.57 meq.; bed-volume=25.0 ml; bed length=49.0 cms. The resin was converted into the chloride form by passing a large excess of sodium chloride solution. The column was then washed free of chloride ions, backwashed and allowed to settle under gravity. Then several bed-volumes of 10% methanol (100 cc. of methanol made to a litre with distilled water) were passed to replace the water in the column. Then the solvent level was brought to the resin bed level and 50 cc. of the solution of coumarin in 10% methanol were passed. The flow rate used in all the runs was 5 cc./minute. When the solution level was again at resin bed level, 10 cc. of the proper eluent were added and then the column was connected to an overhead reservoir of the eluent. The effluent was collected in samples. The first sample, numbered as v.v., was equal to the void volume. After this 100 cc. samples were collected and numbered as 1, 2, 3 and so on. The solute content in the effluent was estimated by ultraviolet absorption³ using Beckman Model DU spectrophotometer and 10 mm. quartz cells. When the run was discontinued, the eluent was further passed, (without collecting the samples) to remove all the sorbed solute. The column was then washed free of the eluent with distilled water, backwashed, allowed to settle under gravity and 10% methanol was passed to replace water in the column. The column was then ready for the next run, and the run was repeated for another compound.

In the separation studies, 50 cc. of the mixture in 10% methanol were passed. When the solution level was at resin bed-level, 10 cc. of the first eluent were added and the column was connected to an overhead reservoir of the first eluent. The eluent was passed to elute

1. Shah, R.S. and Bafna, S. L., *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 179.

2. Shah, R. S. and Bafna, S. L., *Nature*, 1965, 206, 76.

3. Shah, R.S. and Bafna, S. L., *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 400.

the first component. Then the eluent was changed to the second eluent to elute the second component. In the case of ternary mixtures, the eluent was then changed to the third eluent to elute the third component. Then the column was washed free of the eluent, backwashed, allowed to settle and water replaced by passing 10% methanol. Then the procedure was repeated with the next mixture.

Nomenclature:

w = the m mols, of the solute in 50 cc. of solution in 10% methanol, and initially sorbed on the column.

Pw = 100. (mmols, of solute in effluent sample of 100 cc.)/w

R.D. = run discontinued.

a = 10% methanol (prepared by diluting 100 cc. of methanol to one litre with distilled water).

b = N/10 HCl in 10% methanol.

c = N/100 HCl in methanol.

c₁ = m:thanol.

c₂ = 1 N HCl in methanol.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Table I gives the column elution data for coumarin and the substituted coumarins studied. From those data, it is observed that the compounds studied may be broadly divided into three groups: group A includes coumarin (I), 3-Me(I), 7-Me(I), 3, 4-diMe(I), 6,7-diMeO-4-Me(I) and 7,8-diMeO(I); group B includes 7-OH(I) and 8-OH(I) and group C includes 6, 7-diOH-4-Me(I) and 7,8-diOH-4-Me(I). It is observed that group A compounds are eluted with 10% methanol, group B compounds are not eluted with 10% methanol but are slowly eluted with N/10 HCl in 10% methanol and also eluted with N/100 HCl in methanol and group C compounds are not eluted with 10% methanol or with N/10 HCl in 10% methanol but are eluted with N/100 HCl in methanol. Hence it should be possible to separate the binary and ternary mixtures containing not more than one compound from each group.

TABLE I (a)

Column elution data of coumarins

Compound = Coumarin	3-Me (I)	3,4-diMe (I)	7-Me(I)	6,7-diMeO-4-Me(I)	7,8-diMeO(I)	
10 ³ .w =	2.82	2.92	2.88	2.93	2.70	2.77
Eluent =	a	a	a	a	a	a
Sample No.	Pw =	Pw =	Pw =	Pw =	Pw =	Pw =
v.v.	—	—	—	—	—	—
1	—	—	—	—	—	—
2	20.80	6.43	3.38	1.60	8.57	3.20
3	28.05	14.40	8.45	10.10	15.60	11.16
4	21.43	16.08	11.82	16.85	14.00	16.90
5	14.90	16.08	12.16	15.10	11.00	15.95
6	6.11	12.85	11.50	13.50	9.35	12.70
7	4.95	11.26	10.15	11.80	7.80	9.75
8	1.65	8.03	9.50	9.20	7.09	7.50
9	R.D.	6.40	7.60	8.40	6.25	6.00
10		4.82	6.75	6.75	5.45	4.30
11		3.05	5.92	5.00	4.69	3.50
12		R.D.	5.10	R.D.	3.90	2.50
13			4.40		3.12	2.25
14			3.98		R.D.	R.D.
15			R.D.			

TABLE I (b)

Column elution data of coumarins

Com- pound=(I)	7-OH (I)	7-OH (I)	7-OH (I)	7-OH (I)	8-OH (I)	8-OH (I)	6,7-di OH-4- Me(I)	6,7-di OH-4- Me(I)	7,8-di OH-4- Me(I)	7,8-di OH-4- Me(I)
$10^3 \cdot w = 2.82$	2.82	2.90	2.87	2.89	2.75	2.81	2.87	2.90	2.85	2.85
Eluent = a	b	c ₁	c	c ₂	b	c	b	c	b	c
Sample No.	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=	Pw=
v.v.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1	—	—	24.27	58.32	94.13	—	70.21	—	44.64	—
2	—	—	6.13	34.54	4.02	—	24.60	—	42.78	—
3	—	—	4.12	3.88	1.81	—	2.95	—	9.19	—
4	—	—	2.34	2.03	R.D.	1.03	1.91	—	3.10	—
5	—	—	2.10	0.73	—	3.07	R.D.	—	0.12	—
6	—	—	R.D.	R.D.	—	5.60	—	R.D.	—	R.D.
7	—	0.22	—	—	—	7.32	—	—	—	—
8	—	0.53	—	—	—	8.45	—	—	—	—
9	—	1.15	—	—	—	8.90	—	—	—	—
10	—	1.97	—	—	—	8.80	—	—	—	—
11	—	3.00	—	—	—	8.00	—	—	—	—
12	—	3.90	—	—	—	7.23	—	—	—	—
13	—	4.50	—	—	—	6.14	—	—	—	—
14	—	5.20	—	—	—	5.27	—	—	—	—
15	—	5.61	—	—	—	4.56	—	—	—	—
16	—	5.85	—	—	—	4.03	—	—	—	—
17	—	5.98	—	—	—	3.00	—	—	—	—
18	—	6.10	—	—	—	R.D.	—	—	R.D.	—
19	—	5.80	—	—	—	—	R.D.	—	—	—
20	—	5.10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
21	R.D.	5.08	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
22	—	4.99	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
23	—	4.98	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
24	—	4.60	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
25	—	4.31	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
26	—	R.D.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table II gives the binary and ternary mixtures which were studied to illustrate the validity of this procedure.

TABLE II

Separation of some mixtures of coumarins

Mixture No.	First component	Second component	Third component	First component eluted with	After elution of first component, second component eluted with	After elution of second component, third component eluted with
1. Components	=7-Me (I)	+8-OH (I)	—	a	c	—
$10^3 \cdot w$	=1.43	1.41	—	—	—	—
2. Components	=7-Me(I)	+7,8-diOH-4-Me (I)	—	a	c	—
$10^3 \cdot w$	=1.48	1.42	—	—	—	—
3. Components	=6,7-diMeO-4-Me(I)	+8-OH (I)	—	a	c	—
$10^3 \cdot w$	=1.43	1.41	—	—	—	—

TABLE II—(Contd.)

Mixture No.	First component	Second component	Third component	First component eluted with	After elution of first component, second component eluted with	After elution of second component, third component eluted with
4. Components	=6,7-diMeO-4-Me(I)	+7,8-diOH-4-Me(I)	—	a	c	—
10 ² .w	= 1.43	1.42				
5. Components	=8-OH(I)	+7,8-diOH-4-Me(I)	—	b	c	—
10 ² .w	= 1.40	1.42				
6. Components	=7-Me(I)	+8-OH (I)	+7,8-diOH-4-Me(I)	a	b	c
10 ² .w	= 0.872	0.838	1.14			
7. Components	=6,7-diMeO-4-Me(I)	+7-OH(I)	+6,7-diOH-4-Me(I)	a	b	c
10 ² .w	= 0.872	0.845	1.13			

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
M.S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODA.

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